

Participant	Tool	Task Completion (1/0)	Secondary Search query (just querying)	Secondary Search AND access for tool help docs	Secondary source lookup AND access for new secondary sources	Invalid/Alternative Method Tried from main sources	Invalid/Alternative Method Tried from secondary sources (similar to comment to the left)	Valid Method (but from secondary source)	Time Completion (minutes/seconds)	CLI Login Notes
P02	Infisical	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	17:03	
P04	Infisical	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	19:45	
P05	Infisical	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	7:56	
P07	Infisical	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	5:40	only some delay...
P10	Infisical	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	10:39	
P14	Infisical	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	23:42	
P23	Infisical	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	8:31	
Total/Avg		7	4	2	2	3	1	0	13:19	

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P06	Doppler	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	11:52	
P08	Doppler	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	9:43	
P13	Doppler	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	12:17	no
P15	Doppler	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	6:41	intuition to log in and configure came from prior aws experience
P18	Doppler	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	23:28	not important tbh
P19	Doppler	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	22:07	
P21	Doppler	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	10:33	some confusion between login and set up
Total/Avg		7	1	1	0	4	0	0	13:48	

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P02	Infisical	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	Incomplete	120	P02			
P04	Infisical	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5:18	120	P04			
P05	Infisical	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4:04	90	P05			
																MArked because they first got idea from youtube and then went to infisical run command in main docs
P07	infisical	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	16:23	90	P07			
P10	Infisical	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1:04	90	P10			
P14	Infisical	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	Incomplete	120	P14			
P23	Infisical	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2:00	90	P23			
Total/Avg		5	3	3	2	3	0	0	1	1	12:41					

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P01	hcp vault secrets	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	Incomplete	120	P01	
P03	hcp vault secrets	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	12:13	90	P03	
P09	hcp vault secrets	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7:15	90	P09	
P11	hcp vault secrets	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	21:03	120	P11	This one actually did the convoluted way to make it work instead of the direct command... for the most part will just record as a complete unless something pops up
P12	hcp vault secrets	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4:37	60	P12	
P17	HCP vault secrets	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	16:44	90	P17	
P24	hcp vault secrets	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	28:44:00	120	P24	
Total/Avg		6	6	4	5	5	2	2	1	1	17:13			

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P06	Doppler	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	13:28	90	P06	
P08	Doppler	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7:50	90	P08	
P13	Doppler	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	13:20	90	P13	
P15	Doppler	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	23:23	90	P15	
P18	Doppler	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	23:10	120	P18	
P19	Doppler	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	29:05:00	120	P19	
P21	Doppler	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22:51	90	P21	
Total/Avg		7	5	5	5	5	1	1	2	0	19:02:00			